

Agroecology and Sustainable Development in Africa

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ABSTRACT

The term agroecology is not new, since it first appeared in scientific literature in the 1930s. In recent years, it seems to have enjoyed increasing success. It constitutes a new sustainable path for rural development and adaptation to climate change. This study will allow us to assess the impacts of this mode of production and agroecological production techniques.

KEYWORDS: Agroecology, climate change, food security

CONTEXT

The dissemination of agroecological production techniques is an essential stake for sustainable development in Africa. These techniques not only increase the productivity of agriculture but also strengthen its resilience to the effects of climate change. They will help to stem food and nutrition insecurity in the region. Agriculture today faces a number of critical challenges:

- Feed a growing, increasingly urban population.
- Fight against poverty and inequalities.
- Ensure sustainable management of natural resources and the environment.
- Improving food and nutritional security in Africa by taking into account experience in agroecology for the development of resilient agricultural techniques.
- A deteriorating climatic and environmental context for some, agroecology represents one of the most relevant responses to these challenges.

Specific objectives:

Pool and disseminate the practical knowledge and concrete experiences of farmers. Recognize and promote indigenous and local knowledge and practices. Develop links between scientific research and farmers

Impacts:

- Increase in agricultural productivity in the African space
- Strengthening the resilience of agriculture in the face of natural risks
- Mitigation of the effects of climate change.
- Reduction of food insecurity

AGROECOLOGY: CHALLENGES AND ISSUES

Agroecology is above all a scientific discipline at the crossroads of agronomy and ecology. It is also the sum of the

resulting practices. It not only transforms agriculture but also rethinks all food systems to make them more sustainable. It aims to combine agricultural production and reproduction of natural resources. Anchored in local realities, it has both a territorial and a global dimension and can be presented as a system of interactions between the actors involved in the management of farms, sectors and natural resources. It is increasingly implemented around the world and is considered by international bodies as one of the responses to the various challenges.

1- Environmental challenge

This challenge implies respect for a principle of sustainability: Agriculture must not harm natural environments, of which it is an integral part, but on the contrary, seek to enhance their positive interactions. Society must be attentive to the action of agriculture on the environment, which means:

- Restoration of the natural agronomic functions of cultivated ecosystems.
- The fight against soil erosion and the preservation of its fertility.
- Reduction of the consumption of chemical inputs and all exogenous elements of livestock.
- Contribution to mitigation and adaptation to the effects of climate change.

2- Food challenges

This challenge relates to meeting food needs in terms of quantity and quality, an objective that agriculture and the agri-food sector must make it possible to achieve through:

- The production of adequate quality food for the entire population.
- Food sovereignty ensured while respecting food needs.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- ✓ Ensure the effective participation of peasant organizations as well as civil society organizations in the development, establishment and evaluation of any public policy concerning them.
- ✓ Integrate peasant agroecology into the policies and laws of the rural development program, adapted to the context of each country and ensure that these policies are implemented.
- ✓ Mobilize additional public finances specifically oriented towards peasant agroecology.
- ✓ Promote peasant agroecology in international spaces, in particular within the Committee on World Food Security.
- ✓ Give farmers the scientific, technical and financial institutional means to develop their potential in terms of adaptation and resilience in the face of climate change.

CONCLUSION

Agroecology is a new path to sustainable development that allows us to assess the impacts of this mode of production. This technique allows us to increase productivity, but also to strengthen resilience to the effects of climate change. It is the sum of the practices resulting from agronomy and ecology.

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